

INGLIZ VA O'ZBEK TILLARIDA OTLARGA QO'SHILADIGAN KO'PLIK QO'SHIMCHASINING QO'LLANILISHI

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Annotatsiya: mazkur maqolada turli tizimli tillarda ot so'z turkumining ko'plik qo'shimchasining qo'llanishidagi farqli hamda o'xshash jihatlari misollar orqali bayon qilingan.

Kalit so'zlar: ot, ko'plik qoshimchasi, sintaktik usul, morfologik usul

Barcha tillarda bo'lgani kabi ingliz va o'zbek tilidagi ot so'z turkumi o'z ichida bir nechta muhim kategoriyaga bo'linadi: sanaladigan va sanalmaydigan otlar (countable nouns and uncountable nouns), birlik va ko'plik otlar (singular nouns and plural nouns), atoqli va turdosh otlar (common nouns and proper nouns), qo'shma otlar (compound nouns), mavhum otlar (abstract nouns) va jamlovchi otlar (collective nouns).

Biz hozirgi zamon ingliz tilida sanaladigan va sanalmaydigan otlar (countable nouns and uncountable nouns)ning gaplarda ishlatilishi, ularga -s, -es ko'plik affiksi, ko'plikda asoslarning o'zgarishi, asosdan anglashilgan ko'plik qo'shma otlardan ko'plik hosil qilish va a lot of, lots of sintaktik birligining qo'shilishi hamda ularning o'zbek tilidagi tahlillari haqida badiiy adabiyotlardan misollar yig'dik. Tahlil natijalari quyidagilarni ko'rsatadi.

Ingliz tilida odatda otlarni ko'plikka aylantirganda ularga ko'plik hosil qiluvchi -s, -es qo'shimchalari qo'shiladi va bu sodda usul bilan yasalgan ko'plik ot hisoblanadi.

isol uchun: a pen - two pens (pen+s), a shoe - shoes, a tree - five trees va hkz.

-s qo'shimchasi jarangsiz undoshlardan keyin qo'shilganda [s] deb, jarangli undoshlardan keyin kelganda esa [z] deb talaffuz qilinadi.

A map – maps

a cat - cats

a hand- hands

a car- cars

a bag - bags

a table - tables

Agarda ot -o, -s, -ss, -sh, -ch, -z, -x harflari bilan tugaganda, otlarning ko'plik shakli -es qo'shimchasi orqali yasaladi.

One potato-potatoes, a watch-watches, a dish-dishes, a box-boxes, a class-classes va hkz.

-se,-ce,-ze,-ge birikmalari bilan yakunlangan otlarga qo'shilgan -s qo'shimchasi talaffuzda [iz] bo'ladi. Masalan: horse-horses, place places, prize-prizes, cage-cages, -o harfi bilan tugagan otlarga -es qo'shimchasi qo'shiladi deb aytgandik (tomato-tomatoes, hero-heroes, cargo-cargoes), ammo istisno holatlari mavjud, ya'ni boshqa tillardan o'zlashgan -o bilan tugaydigan so'zlarning ko'plik soni -s qo'shish orqali shakllantiriladi:

video-videos

memo-memos

kangaroo-kangaroos

tobacco-tobaccos

ghetto-ghettos

hippo-hippos

ZOO-ZOOS

photo-photos

Eslatma sifatida aytish kerakki, quyidagi otlarning ko'plik formasi ixtiyoriy ravishda ham -s ham -es qo'shish orqali yasaladi:

Momento-momentos/momentoes

Volcano-volcanos/volcanoes

Mosquito-mosquitos/mosquitoes

Zero-zeros/zeroes

Tornado-tornados/tornadoes

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Agar ot oxiri (-f,-fe) bilan tugasa, unda -f/-fe -v ga aylanib -es qo'shiladi: Half-halves, calf-calves, leaf-leaves, wolf-wolves, thief-thieves Istisno: garchand quyidagi otlarning oxiri -f,-fe harflari bialn tugasada, ularning ko'plik shakli yoki -ves, yoki -s qo'shish orqali yasaladi.

Scarf-scarves/scarfs

Hoof-hooves/hoofs

dwarf-dwarves/dwarfs

wharf-wharves/wharfs

Quyidagi otlarning ko'plik shakli ot o'zaginging o'zgarishi orqali hosil qilinadi: Man-men,

woman-women,

tooth- teeth,

person-people,

foot-feet,

child-children,

data-datum,

mouse-mice,

memoranda-memorandum,

basis-bases,
ox-oxen,
erratum-errata,
criterion -criteria,

formula-formulae,
bacterium-bacteria,
chick- chicken va boshqala

Collective nouns (jamlovchi otlar)da asosdan ko'plik ma'nosi anglashilib turadi. Masalan: the police- politsiya jamoasi ichida bir nechta politsiya xodimlari xizmat qilishadi, army-armiya, family-oila, government, staff, generation, association, department, community, band, population, council va boshqalar.

Chiziqcha bilan ajratib yoziladigan qo'shma otlarning asosiy ma'no beruvchi qismi ko'plikda kela oladi: Custom-house - custom-houses , passer-by - passers-by, mother-in-law - mothers-in-laws, man-in-war - men-in-wars

Qo'shib yoziladigan qo'shma otlarning ikkinchi so'ziga ko'plik qo'shimchasi qo'shiladi. Misol uchun, Schoolboy-schoolboys , housewife-housewives

Ingliz tilida moddiy va mavhum otlar sanalmaydi. Ya'ni, masalan: knowledge, oil, milk, money, bread, economics, work, air, advertising va hkz. Ularga odatda ko'plik qo'shimchasi qo'shilmaydi. Ammo istisno holatlarda:

-moddalardan yasalgan buyumni ifodalab kelganda sanaladigan ot kategoriyasiga o'tib ko'plik qo'shimchasini qabul qiladi: Misol uchun, Two bricks and broken pieces of bottle suddenly emerged in the light of our lamps.

•moddaning har xil navini va turini ifodalaganda ko'plik qo'shimchasini qabul qila oladi: misol uchun, He prefers Caucasian wines to Crimean wines.

• Ba zida mavhum otlar konkretlashib keladi va sanaladigan otga almashib ko'plik affikslarini qabul qiladi: misol uchun, The speeches of Mr.Dupin are always interesting.

Huddi ingliz tilidagidek, o'zbek tilida ham otlarning ko'plik shakllarini hosil qilish ularga -lar lug aviy shakl yasovchi qo'shimchasi yordamida, asosdan anglashilgan ko'plik yoki so'zlar takrori orqali yasaladi. Bu usullar grammatik ko'plikni hosil qiladi. Masalan: kitob - kitoblar, uy- uylar, sovg'a -sovg alar va h.z.

Bundan tashqari so zlarni juftlash orqali ham ko'plik ma nosini anglanishi mumkin: to'da-to'da, uyum-uyum, qat-qat, yum-yum va boshqalar.

Kumushbibi ichini o'rtayotgan hasratlardan bekinib yum-yum yig'lardi. (ushbu gapda yum-yum so'zi ko'p yig'laganini bildiryapti ya'ni mantiqiy ko'plik anglashilyapti) Sintaktik yo'l bilan ya'ni bunda ko'plik ma'nosi otlardan oldin birdan yuqori bo'lgan sanoq sonlarni va daraja-miqdor ravishlarini keltirish bilan hosil qilinadi: ko'p kitob, bir nechta kitob, bir talay kitob, beshta kitob. Semantik ko'plik - hech qanday qo'shimchalarsiz ma'no ichida ko'plikning

mavjudligidir (ingliz tilidagi Collective nouns). Masalan: xalq, armiya, poda, jamoa, guruh, olomon, aholi kabi so'zlar.

O'zbek tilida mavhum va sanalmaydigan otlar tub yoki -inch, -ot,-lik va boshqa qo'shimchalar yordamida yasalgan bo'lishi mumkin: zavq, bilim, sog'lik, sog'inch, sevinch, kamolot, yaxshilik, yomonlik va h.k. Ularga qo'shiladigan -lar ko'plik qo'shimchasi ko'plik hosil qilish uchun emas, balki ma'no kuchaytirish, tasviriylik ifodalilik uchun xizmat qiladi. Sizlarga qarab zavqlarim toshib ketdi.

Tumanimiz markazida yog'lar ishlab chiqarilmoqda.

Boshlarim og'rib ketdi (aslida insonda bitta bosh mavjud -lar qo'shimchasi ma'no kuchaytiriyapti).

A lot of, lots of sintaktik birliklari esa noaniq miqdorni ko'rsatib kelib, ham sanaladigan, ham sanalmaydigan otlar oldidan ishlatilib ularga ko'plik ma'nosini qo'shadi.

There'd been a lot of blocks science, but they hadn't lasted she was growing out of Horrible Hackney and it's young man. (J. Fowles, Daniel Martin 299)

"You know what I mean», she said, finally as if there were lots of information which she held in reserve - which she did not need to tell. (T.Dreiser, Sister Carrie, 188)

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